

Lidar OEM 'State of the Nation'

Matthew Smith
Senior Sales Manager

How we are supporting the industry

- Facilitating a practical approach to project development, improving “bankability”, improving turbine OEM Lidar acceptance
 - Managing uncertainty in measurements
 - Eliminating CW directional uncertainty
 - Lidar Turbulence measurement and wind turbine OEM acceptance
 - Lifting the limits on Lidar verifications imposed by mast height

Managing uncertainties in Lidar measurements

- Uncertainty is the key tool available to Developers to justify measurement costs.
- The IEC Classification process manages the **environmental sensitivities** associated with measurement uncertainty.
- In 2024 and 2025, **ZX 300e's** were deployed at approved IEC test sites: Hanover (Geo-Net), Janneby (Pavana) and the UK Remote Sensing Test Site (ZX & DNV).
- ZX 300e Classification: 21m to 200m, IEC 61400-50-2 compliant methodology.
- 5 campaigns, 3 Lidars and 3 test sites.
- **No significant environmental variables found resulting in a final accuracy class and standard uncertainty of 0% at all heights from 21 – 200m for ZX 300e.**
- **Allows this component of measurement uncertainty to be reduced. Does this help?**

Height (m)	Class (%)	Std Uncertainty (%)
200	0	0
190	0	0
180	0	0
170	0	0
160	0	0
150	0	0
140	0	0
130	0	0
120	0	0
110	0	0
100	0	0
90	0	0
80	0	0
70	0	0
60	0	0
50	0	0
40	0	0
30	0	0
21	0	0

Eliminating CW directional uncertainty

- Previous CW Lidars have occasional directional ambiguity under certain wind flow conditions
 - Extra processing required, generally no additional uncertainty added
 - Using the mast as a reference the differences between 10-minute averaged wind directions measured by the mast and the fleet of lidars was computed
 - **ZX 300e accurately measures wind direction to within +/- 0.5 degree**
 - No direction ambiguity, no need to further process any measured data
 - Onboard met station still available
-
- **Makes handling of data easier. Does this help?**

Cup-equivalent Turbulence Intensity validation

- A fresh approach to comparison between cup TI and Lidar TI
- ZX ‘METICE’: Multi-site Ensemble Turbulent Intensity Cup Equivalence leveraging Artificial Neural Network and Models
- Can be used on any ZX Wind10 data file to produce new TI outputs
- Evaluated across more than 17 sites...and counting, simple and complex terrain, and with varying stability conditions
- We need more data, more ZX data sets, more ‘high quality mast datasets.
- Why? To support ongoing wind turbine OEM acceptance of Lidar TI and address barriers for adoption
- Support use cases: EYA, power performance measurements, load calculations, lifetime extension

21/06 - 23/09/25	Hanover ZX6003							
Height (m)	59	79	99	119	139	159	179	199
TI Gradient [0.95<X<1.05]	1.000	1.004	1.001	0.988	0.987	0.962	0.960	1.000
TI R-squared [X > 0.7]	0.934	0.925	0.904	0.884	0.876	0.770	0.718	0.785
TI R-squared (DNV)	0.989	0.984	0.977	0.970	0.967	0.934	0.915	0.932

23/05 - 13/08/25	Hanover ZX6004							
Height (m)	59	79	99	119	139	159	179	199
TI Gradient [0.95<X<1.05]	0.999	1.000	1.008	0.999	0.993	0.993	0.992	1.012
TI R-squared [X > 0.7]	0.919	0.915	0.900	0.888	0.869	0.824	0.799	0.751
TI R-squared (DNV)	0.990	0.986	0.980	0.976	0.970	0.957	0.948	0.930

17/02/25 - 18/05/25	Pavana ZX6002								
Height (m)	39	59	79	99	119	139	159	179	199
TI Gradient [0.95<X<1.05]	0.990	0.983	1.007	1.011	0.998	1.002	1.030	1.024	1.020
TI R-squared [X > 0.7]	0.901	0.907	0.879	0.852	0.847	0.821	0.777	0.765	0.744
TI R-squared (DNV)	0.991	0.987	0.980	0.973	0.970	0.962	0.945	0.939	0.928

19/02/25 - 20/05/25	Pavana ZX6003								
Height (m)	39	59	79	99	119	139	159	179	199
TI Gradient [0.95<X<1.05]	0.998	0.993	1.013	1.019	1.005	1.014	1.039	1.032	1.031
TI R-squared [X > 0.7]	0.893	0.907	0.883	0.844	0.844	0.812	0.783	0.758	0.735
TI R-squared (DNV)	0.991	0.987	0.981	0.972	0.970	0.960	0.947	0.938	0.928

10/10/24 - 08/01/25	Persore ZX6101			
Height (m)	20	45	70	91
TI Gradient [0.95<X<1.05]	0.998	0.985	0.990	1.006
TI R-squared [X > 0.7]	0.792	0.879	0.861	0.817
TI R-squared (DNV)	0.991	0.991	0.985	0.976

23/05 - 13/08/25	Janneby ZX6101			
Height (m)	28	56	74	102
TI Gradient [0.95<X<1.05]	0.934	0.958	0.961	0.968
TI R-squared [X > 0.7]	0.671	0.847	0.852	0.828
TI R-squared (DNV)	0.986	0.985	0.982	0.975

Lifting the limits on Lidar verifications due to mast height

- Could collective trust in Lidar be leveraged to go beyond existing mast verification heights?
- At Pershore (IEC compliant site) a Lidar was verified against the 91m met mast, and against reference Lidars (200m mast traceability with known and low uncertainties, 0% standard Classification uncertainty.)
- Verified Lidar then mounted at the top of the 91m met mast to extend the mast range.
- This **Midar** ('Mast' + 'Lidar') configuration allows additional ground-based lidar verifications to be traceable against verified references (mast and Midar) up to 300m above ground level
- **Accuracy and data availability analysed across a ZX300e fleet with all industry KPI's met and exceeded up to and including 300m.**
- **Green = DNV best practice, Orange = DNV minimum acceptance criteria**
- **Does this help?**

How can Task 52 help?

- As a mechanism to drive global Lidar adoption and unlock Lidar benefits
- BUT, are established methodologies appropriate for project development in anywhere in the world?
- Are we attracting unnecessary uncertainties?
- Not all countries have high masts!

- **How do we better engage the international community to ensure that best practice and standards developed are suitable for all wind markets?**

With **ZX300e**
we raise the benchmark again.